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EVALUATING THE PREFERENCES AND EFFECTIVENESS OF DIFFERENT ONLINE BREAST CANCER HEALTHCARE INFORMATION PRESENTATION FORMATS.

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ABSTRACT

The capacity of Internet to serve as a virtual clinical house for communicating health information enable people with common health interests to maintain electronic contact. The Internet is an important source of Breast Cancer Health Care information which can provide people valuable information and guidance. The purpose of this study was to investigate what types of online BHC presentation formats communicating with Taiwanese women were more effectively. The methods included three phases: the first phase was "document method" to generalize the communication types of online BHC, 183 female subjects (47% under 34 years old, 53% over 35 years old) were participated in this survey; the second phase was questionnaire method to understand women's preference of online BHC formats; the last phase was In-depth interview method with medical professions and web design experts to understand the most effective online BHC presentation format. The results were as follows:

- 1) The quality and reliability of information provided by the website affect the participant access to it.
- 2) Currently, the formats of online health education information presentation were the formats with non-interactive features such as the text-based, the image type and the chart type.
- 3) Online BHC information with text format was the most favorite format to the subjects under 34 years old, and Video format was the most

attractive and comprehensible to the subjects over 35 years old.

4) The experts indicated that the most effective online BHC information was video format, which included interactive characteristics such as "Easy to Use", "Direct Operation" and "Animation Simulation".

The results of this research will enable website designers to understand the correct triggers to use in for affective and effective online BHC design and also provides an effective research methodology for further research in affective online health education information design.

Keywords: Online, Breast Cancer Health Care (BHC) Information, Web Design.

INTRODUCTION

Breast cancer is one of the cancers that can be easily detected at early stage, therefore, the most effective health education approach and presentation form are to arouse women's self-awareness of health and provide them with self-examination methods. Health information is the most important resource for health care and health promotion because it is an important guiding strategy for treatment and decision-making (Kreps, 1988). Consumer use of the Internet for health information is large and growing; more than 70,000 websites provide health information (Grandinetti, 2000; R. J. W. Cline & K. M. Haynes, 2001). Websites are important sources for health information (Hesse et al., 2005), and more than half of all Taiwanese women have had the experience or need to search

for online breast self-examination (BSE) information, which shows that online hygiene education information has become a channel for learning and testing (Lin F. S. et al, 2010).

Traditionally, the two strategies frequently used for health promotion are: first, increase the provision of health information and health services, while lowering environmental risks, and second, use health information, education, and communication (IEC) (Kar et al., 1999) to inspire the desire for people to pursue health, and in turn increase their usage of health services. As a promotional strategy for health education information, the Department of Health (DOH), Executive Yuan of Taiwan began in 1988 the “establishment of a national healthcare information web” project. Furthermore, in view of the trend of increasing online health information, in order to ensure the accuracy and reliability of online health information, to meet needs of the general public regarding health maintenance information. In the year of 2002, the DOH began promoting the annual selection of health information websites, and established good information entry websites (<http://awards.doh.gov.tw/>) for the general public to search for health care information.

Bruce (1998) defined the search for online information as “To search and solve questions via Internet and a purposive and interactive behavior with online resources.” Deering and Harris (1996) classified consumer health information as any information that can allow consumers understand their own health and make decisions relating to the health of themselves or their family members. Robinson et al. (1998) pointed out “interactive health communication” as “the interaction of an individual-consumer, patient, caregiver or professional-with or through an electronic device or communication technology to access or transmit health information or to receive guidance and support on a health-related issue. (R. J. W. Cline & K. M. Haynes, 2001)”

Based on the “Survey on the Number of Internet Users in Taiwan” conducted by FIND Network Information Center, Bureau of Promotion, Institute for Information Industry, as commissioned by Division NII, Department of Industrial Technology, Ministry of

Economic Affairs, and the “Investigation on the Internet Usage” published by Department of Statistics, Ministry of Communications in March 2007, it was found that three main purposes of the use of Internet are: “to browse/search information,” “to browse online news,” and “to send and receive e-mails.” Moreover, the research of Pew Research Center’s Internet & American Life Project and the California HealthCare Foundation (2009) indicated that 61% of the adults have searched online health information, and 59% have at least engaged in the following five activities online:

- Reading the comments or experiences concerning health or medical issues of other people via online news community, websites, or blogs.
- Consulting highly ranked or rated online doctors and other information providers.
- Consulting highly ranked or rated hospitals and other medical institutions.
- Visiting websites that regularly update and receiving health or medicine-related information.
- Browsing the Podcast relevant to health or medicine issues.

Increasingly, consumers engage in health care information seeking through Internet. Concerns about the quality of online healthcare information, several studies of single medical conditions have suggested deficiencies in the quality of Web-based health information (Davison K, 1997; Beredjiklian et al., 2000; Biemann et al., 2000). Some organizations have developed criteria to guide and evaluate health-related Website content (Harris poll, 1999; Health on the Net Foundation, 2011).

According to the data in epidemiology, having breast cancer in women generally occurs after menopause in Europe and America, while in Taiwan approximately 50% of breast cancer cases occur before age 50; compared to the cases in Europe and America, breast cancer occurs earlier in Taiwan, approximately between 45-64 years of age (Department of Health, Executive Yuan, 2007). The possible causes of breast cancer may vary among different people; yet, among the single risk factors, the main factor is age (Vogel, 1991; Vogel, 2003; Vogel, 2004; Gierach et al., 2004; Althuis et al., 2004; Ferrer et al., 2005). American Cancer Society also

lists the childbearing age of women (over 35) as an indicator for analyzing the risk factors for breast cancer. Thus, in view of the fact that the peak age of breast cancer has gradually decreased, the perspective of preventative medicine is employed to survey the needs and preferences for online breast cancer health care (BCHC) information of Taiwanese women in age groups of below 34 and over 35. Expert interviews and questionnaire survey were used to understand the characteristics of online breast cancer prevention and health education information presentation forms. There are three purposes of this study:

- Establish current classifications of expression forms and functional characteristics of online breast cancer prevention and health education information.
- The preferential differences regarding expression forms of online health education information among Taiwanese women in different age groups.
- The research results can be provided as references for the design of online health education information, to achieve the efficacy of communication.

METHOD

There were three stages in the methodology of this study:

- First stage: this study conducted literature review to collect and organize online data relating to the topic of this study, in order to summarize the forms of expression and functional characteristics of online information. Between November 2009 and February 2010, the Google search engine was used to input the keyword “BSE,” which yielded 56 websites with health care information relating to breast cancer. Among them, 24 websites on breast cancer medical information along with healthcare information including “breast self-examinations” were used as the online health education information samples for this study, and 33 university students with a design background categorized the forms of expression and the functional characteristics.
- Second stage: A questionnaire survey was used to understand the preference of Taiwanese women regarding the form of expression of online BCHC

information. In view of the fact that the peak age of breast cancer has gradually decreased, this study divided subjects into two groups, those under 34 years of age and those over 35 years of age. A total of 200 paper and electronic questionnaires were released, convenience sampling was used, and female subjects filled out the questionnaires. After discarding 17 invalid questionnaires that were incomplete, 183 valid questionnaires were retrieved, yielding 183 female subjects. SPSS statistical software was used for software processing of data encoding and statistical analysis, in which the t-test was used to explore differences in Taiwanese women’s “preferences for the form of expression of online BCHC information.”

- Third stage: this study used in-depth expert interviews for seven experts with over five years in design experience relating to website design, in order to understand the efficacy of forms of expression in online BCHC information, and summarized their unique points. Finally, this study summarized the research results to propose design suggestions for the forms of optimal online health education information used to achieve the effect of communication.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSTION

THE FORMS AND FUNCTIONS OF ONLINE BCHC INFORMATION

In the first stage of this study, 56 websites with health care information relating to breast cancer were collected, and the 24 websites with BSE-related health care information were used as the sample for health education information in this study (Table 1). Websites primarily provide viewers with integrated information, in order to communicate with the public, and interactive functions are the most important trait of the internet that differs from other communications media (Griffith & Krampf , 1998; Willianms, Rice & Rogers, 1998). In the planning of digital multimedia design, information design is the channel for presenting the information and conveying communication. The information image includes maps, charts, and images; knowledge is transmitted visually rather than as text (Jenifer

Classification of BCHC information communication through Internet N=33 (N / %)										
No. of samples	Forms					Functions				
	Text	Image	Diagram	Video	Animation	Switching	Editing	Saving	Interaction	None
1	●33/100									●33/100
2	3/9	14/42	▲16/48			9/27	6/18	12/36	1/3	4/12
3	●33/100									●33/100
4		●28/84	5/15							●33/100
5		●33/100						●33/100		
6	●28/84	4/12	1/3			●28/84	2/6	1/3		2/6
7	●25/75	7/21	1/3			●25/75	3/9	3/9		2/6
8		●24/72	9/27							●33/100
9		8/24	●25/75			●33/100				
10	5/15	8/24	▲20/60							●33/100
11	2/6	9/27	▲22/66							●33/100
12	●33/100					3/9	▲18/54		9/27	2/6
13	●24/72		9/27			1/3			●32/96	
14				●33/100					●33/100	
15				●32/96	1/3				●33/100	
16				●33/100					●33/100	
17			1/3		●32/96				●33/100	
18	15/45		▲18/54						●33/100	
19		1/3	2/6	▲16/48	14/42				●33/100	
20		●24/72	7/21			8/24	1/3		13/39	11/33
21					●33/100				●33/100	
22	●28/84	5/15				●31/93				2/6
23	15/45	2/6	▲16/48			●24/72	3/9			6/18
24	●32/96	1/3				2/6				●31/93

Meanings of the symbols: ●>70% ▲>40%

Table 1. Statistics of Classification of Online BCHC Information Presentation Forms

Tidwell, 2006), and digital images are processed by the computer. Thus, the display form of digital images is used to construct a virtual learning environment on the World Wide Web. The other unique trait of digital multimedia is that it has the effect of animation. Morimoto (1993) pointed out that the animation method can convey the semantic meaning of images, referred to as dynamic images. Vaughan (1993) proposed that the animated effects of websites can attract user’s attention, and in turn pay attention on the screen; the dynamic images would also change with time, to express the functional meaning, formats, or conversions of images. Beekman (1994) suggested that hypertext is a type of text document that can be read on the screen and includes annotated words or phrases, with the function of linking to related documents. Hypermedia includes hypertext, as well as images, sounds, and videos. Tillman (1997) has stressed the importance of using images to replace just text presentations. Wu (1999) pointed out that computer multimedia is done through the information technology such as computer, video transmission, and communications for assistance, and digital technology is used to digitally edit, save, and convert texts, charts, static images, dynamic video

recordings, computer animation, background information, narration, and digital sound effects; these are used for comprehensive presentation or as ways to accentuate concepts. Websites primarily provide viewers with integrated information, in order to communicate with the public, and interactive functions are the most important trait of the internet that differs from other communications media (Griffith & Krampf, 1998; Williams, Rice & Rogers, 1998).

Having compiled literature from the scholars above, this study used forms of online expression in terms of expression form and functional characteristics as the way this study divided categories of online hygiene education information items; there were five expression forms: 1) Text: static text; 2) Image: static images, dynamic images; 3) Diagram: image and charts; 4) Video: video and sound; 5) Animation: dynamic images produced from digital technology or software. Functional characteristics consider digital design technology and settings, which include four types: 1) Switching: hypertext, hyperlinks, opening new windows, conversion of images; 2) Editing: online questionnaire-style testing; 3) Saving: article

saving and e-mail, online instant printing; 4) Interaction: control of button objects, control of media.

Thirty-three university students in design department in Taiwan participated in research classification, and the classification results were used to summarize expression forms and functional characteristics of online breast cancer prevention and health education information. At the current

time, the expression forms of online hygiene education information generally do not have Interactive functional characteristics, such as “Text,” “Image,” “Diagram,” and simple “Text” forms. The “Text” form generally combines with images and forms without interactive display; online breast cancer prevention and health education information should not just have textual descriptions like print media, and should be expressed through internet multimedia characteristics; “Video” and

Form	Content of Online Information Communication			
Text				
Original No.	1	3	12	
New No.	A01	A02	A03	
Function	None (●>70%)	None (●>70%)	Editing (▲>40%)	
Image				
Original No.	5	4	8	20
New No.	B01	B02	B03	B04
Function	Saving (●>70%)	None (●>70%)	None (●>70%)	Insignificant
Diagram				
Original No.	9	11	10	
New No.	C01	C02	C03	
Function	Switching	None (●>70%)	None (●>70%)	
Video				
Original No.	14	16	15	
New No.	D01	D02	D03	
Function	Interaction (●>70%)	Interaction (●>70%)	Interaction (●>70%)	
Animation				
Original No.	21	17		
New No.	E01	E02		
Function	Interaction (●>70%)	Interaction (●>70%)		

Table 2. Classification of Online BCHC Information Presentation Forms and Function

“Animation” are both interactive.

Results in the first stage of research apply the expression forms of online health education information in the questionnaire design in the second stage of research, used to understand the preference of Taiwanese women for online health education information expression forms. This study further extracted top 3 samples in each type and re-encodes them for the discussion (Table 2):

Functions of text

A01, A02 and A03 are generalized as text. A01 and A02 display the information by static text and describe the principle and practice of breast self-examination by text. They both do not involve digital design technique and setting. A03 is based on online questionnaire, and the users select the proper answers according to the items which include basic information, living habit, family history and risk. Finally, the researcher generalized the users' current risk and encouraged users to have self-examination on line. Thus, the sample is regarded as editing function.

Functions of image

B01, B02, B03 and B04 are classified as images. B01 shows the information by graphic illustration, simulates the scope and movement of breast self-examination and it involves the functions of text saving, Email and online printing. Thus, it is regarded as saving function; B02 and B03 show the process of breast self-examination by static image and they do not involve digital design technique and setting; B04 is online database of medical images and the function is insignificant.

Functions of figure

C01, C02 and C03 are classified as figures. C01 shows the information by tables and figures and describes the principle and process of breast self-examination by images and texts. It is connected with new pages by hyper text and thus is allocated as the conversion function; C02 and C03 shows the information by the images and texts of the tables and figures and they do not involve digital design technique and setting.

Functions of video

D01, D02 and D03 are classified as videos. D01 and D03 show the information by 3D and simulate the animated instruction of breast structure and self-examination process; D02 includes animated simulation and real person demonstration to explain the animated instruction of breast self-examination. It involves button control and setting of control media and thus is allocated as interaction function.

Functions of animation

E01 and E02 are classified as animation. E01 shows the information by Flash, including breast cancer information instruction and online test; E02 presents the information by animated images to explain the steps of breast self-examination. It involves button control and setting of control media and thus is allocated as interaction function.

THE SURVEY OF PRESENTATION FORM OF ONLINE BCHC INFORMATION TO RESPONDENTS

The second stage of this study focused on the views of 183 subjects on the expression forms of online BCHC information. In the questionnaire items, to make “Animation” easy to understand, the category was divided into “Interactive Game” and “Online Animation,” which were used to understand the preferences of subjects for online breast cancer prevention information.

This study divided subjects into two groups, those under 34 years of age (47%) and those over 35 years of age (53%). Based on the data analysis, the age distribution of the subjects was 25-39 (24.6%). Most of the subjects had university (33.9%) or graduate school education (31.1%), and were working in public office, educational field (38.3%), and the field of business (21.3%).

The factors of “the favorite presentation form of online medical information content” and “the most comprehensible presentation form of online medical information content” had significant influences (Table 3). For the respondents under the age of 34 and their favorite presentation forms are in the order as follows: “Text” (36.0%), “Online Animation”

Items	Groups	Text	Image	Diagram	Video	Animation		Total N=183	t
						Interactive Game	Online Animation		
The most favorite presentation forms	≤34years	31	0	6	16	15	18	86	-2.21*
		36.0%	.0%	7.0%	18.6%	17.4%	20.9%	100.0%	
	≥35years	34	2	1	12	11	37	97	
		35.1%	2.1%	1.0%	12.4%	11.3%	38.1%	100.0%	
The most attractive presentation forms	≤34years	25	0	3	20	22	16	86	-1.25
		29.1%	.0%	3.5%	23.3%	25.6%	18.6%	100.0%	
	≥35years	22	2	0	25	17	31	97	
		22.7%	2.1%	.0%	25.8%	17.5%	32.0%	100.0%	
The most comprehensible presentation forms	≤34years	24	1	3	30	14	14	86	-2.41*
		27.9%	1.2%	3.5%	34.9%	16.3%	16.3%	100.0%	
	≥35years	28	2	0	22	9	36	97	
		28.9%	2.1%	.0%	22.7%	9.3%	37.1%	100.0%	

Table 3. The survey of presentation form of online BCHC information content to respondents

(20.9%), and “Video” (18.6%). For the respondents over the age of 35, the favorite presentation forms are in the order as follows: “Online Animation” (38.1%), “Text” (35.1%), and “Video” (12.4%).

*P<.05 **P<.01 ***P<.001

The women under the age of 34 suggested that the most attractive presentation forms are in the order as follows: “Text” (29.1%), “Interactive Game” (25.6%), and “Video” (23.3%), while those over the age of 35 suggested that the most attractive ones were in the order as follows: “Online Animation” (32.0%), “Video” (25.8%), and “Text” (22.7%).

The women under the age of 34 suggested that the most comprehensible presentation forms were in the

order as follows: “Video” (34.9%), “Text” (27.9%), “Interactive Game”, and “Online Animation” (both 16.3%). The women over the age of 35 suggested that the most comprehensible presentation forms were “Online Animation” (37.1%), “Tex” (28.9%), and “Video” (22.7%). Therefore, it was found that the women under the age of 34 also suggested that favorite and the most attractive information presentation form was “Text”, followed by “Online Animation”. The women over the age of 35 suggested that the most attractive and comprehensible presentation form was “Online Animation”.

Subject	Gender	Education	Longevity	Type of department	Position	Working content
F1	F	University★	10	Design department of small and medium-size enterprise	Design Director	Web Design, Graphic Design
F2	M	University★	5	Design department of small and medium-size enterprise	Designer	Web Design, Graphic Design
F3	M	University★	7	Design department of small and medium-size enterprise	Section Chief	Web Design, Graphic Design
F4	M	University★	6	Administrative department of public university	Project Assistant	Multimedia, Web, Graphic, 3D
F5	F	University★	15	Design department of small and medium-size enterprise	Designer	Web Design, Graphic Design
F6	M	College▲	13	Design department of small and medium-size enterprise	Manager	Web Design, Graphic Design
F7	M	Master●	7	Management department of small and medium-size enterprise	Project Manager	Planning, Web management

★Visual Communication design, ▲Commercial Design, ●Industrial Design

Table 4. The basic data of interviewing Experts background

Items		Factors	The opinions of experts	Subjects
The most favorite presentation forms	Video	Richness	The video and sound has actual examples, the information includes images and texts, while actions are presented dynamically, so the presentation methods are more definitive, lively, and rich.	F 1、F 2、F 4、F 5、F 6、F 7
	Animation	Liveliness	The animation form can convert serious health education content into more relaxed and lively expressions for the user.	F 3
The most attractive presentation forms	Video	Sensory	The video and sound types include sight and sound influences, so that the dynamic presentation or simulations are better at attracting attention.	F 1、F 2、F 4、F 5、F 6、F 7
	Animation	Liveliness	The animation form can be used to design cuter and more relaxed animation, and with livelier elements.	F 3
The most comprehensible presentation forms	Video	Completeness	The video and sound form includes more complete dynamic explanations and information, thus it is easier to understand.	F 1、F 2、F 3、F 5、F 6、F 7
	Animation	Comparability	Text with simple animation is most easily understood.	F 4
The most easy to learn presentation forms	Video	Repetition	The video and sound type is more intuitive, direct, and can be repeatedly played, so that users are less likely to mistakenly understand images. The users find it easier to learn hygiene education information.	F 1、F 2、F 3、F 4、F 6、F 7
	Table	Comparability	Some health education information contains data, so it is easier to understand with images and text.	F 5
The most easy to memorize presentation forms	Video	Richness	The video and sound type has dynamic images, along with explanations, pictures, text, and subtitles, which are better at helping people remember health education information.	F 1、F 2、F 5、F 7
	Animation	Simulation	Pictures, with video and sound make up the most direct method, because dynamic simulation can enhance memory.	F 4、F 6
	Image	Simplicity	The simple images are easily remembered by people.	F 3
The most easy to use Interface presentation forms	Video	Intuitiveness	The public is familiar with the video and sound type operational icons and can intuitively operate, select, and browse.	F 2、F 3、F 7
	Image	Simplicity	Understandable when seen, easy to select, complicated operations are not necessary.	F 5、F 6
	Text	Simplicity	The simplest and basic form. Traditional text should be most easily manipulated.	F 1、F 4

Table 5. The opinions of presentation form of online BCHC information content to Experts

THE INTERVIEWS OF PRESENTATION FORM OF ONLINE BCHC INFORMATION TO EXPERTS

In the third stage, this study used in-depth expert interviews for seven experts with over five years in design experience (Table 4), in order to understand the efficacy of forms of expression in online BCHC information of “Text,” “Image,” “Diagram,” “Video,” and “Animation,” and the expert opinions were used to summarize their characteristics (Table 5).

The most favorite presentation forms

Six experts believed that “Video” displays the dynamic examples, and have a clearer, more dynamic, and rich presentation method. Only interview subject F3 preferred “Animation,” believing that it could actively convert the

BCHC information from serious health education content into a lively form.

The most attractive presentation forms

Six experts believed that it is “Video,” because it includes visual and audio presentation that is more likely to attract attention of the user. Only interview subject F3 believed that “Animation” can use cute and lively animated images to attract attention.

The most comprehensible presentation forms

Six experts believed that “Video” can use rich images, texts, and sounds to present comprehensive health education information, thereby making it easier for users to understand. Only interview subject F4 believed that “Animation” with images and texts make comprehension easier for users.

The most easy to learn presentation forms

Six experts believed that the form “Video” is the form easiest to learn from, since the information is clearly and directly displayed, and it can be replayed and browsed, it is beneficial for user learning. Interview subject F5 believed that “Diagram” can be easily learned from when there are data numbers in BCHC information, which are presented as text with corresponding images.

The most easy to memorize presentation forms

Four experts believed that since “Video” includes dynamic images, explanations and subtitles, and texts and corresponding pictures, the diverse display is relatively better at making an impression on user memory. Interview subjects F4 and F6 believed that in “Animation,” pictures with images and sounds can help with memory. Only interview subject F3 believed that in “Image” the simple images can lead to ease of memory.

The most easy to use interface presentation forms

Interview subjects F2, F3, and F7 believed that the operation icons in “Video” are well-known by the public and they can intuitively operate, select, and browse. Interview subjects F5 and A6 believed that the simple images in “Image” are easy to select, and the complicated operation procedures are reduced. Finally, interview subjects F1 and A4 believed that the most traditional “Text” is convenient and easy to operate.

Finally, summarization of the expert opinions shows that preferable websites should be rich and lively; attractive website forms should be sensory and lively. The most easily understood website form should focus on the completeness and comparability of the content. Websites that are easy to learn from should have repetition and comparability to achieve the purpose of learning health education. Websites that are rich, simulated, and simple can best help one remember the effectiveness of the health education. As for the usage problems of interface operation, the experts propose that intuitiveness and simplicity can best achieve the effect of easy use.

CONCLUSION

Breast cancer prevention and health education information is a key point in women’s health promotion and disease prevention policies in Taiwan. Under the influence of medical care consciousness, information needs, and the digital age, the internet has become a medium for the promotion of health education information. This study conducts three stages of investigation, which helped to obtain the current expression forms of online breast cancer prevention and health education information, as well as the information preferred by Taiwanese women, and finally the expert interviews are used to understand the characteristics of presentation forms of information. The conclusion was as follows:

- Currently, the expression forms of online health education information do not usually have interactive functional characteristics, such as “Text,” “Image,” and “Diagram.” Online BCHC information should apply more internet multimedia characteristics; among them “Video” and “Animation” are both interactive.
- In Taiwan, women below 34 years of age preferred and thought that online health education information expressed as “Text” was best at attracting attention, followed by “Online Animation.” Women over 35 years of age thought that the form of “Online Animation” was best at attracting attention and being understood.
- Experts generally pointed out that they most preferred the online health education information presentation form of “Video,” believing that it can best attract attention, was easiest to understand and remember, and followed by “Animation.”
- Experts indicated that the presentation form of “Video” is rich, sensory, complete, repetitive, and intuitive, with the interactive characteristics of “Easy to Use,” “Direct Operation,” and “Animation Simulation,” that can best achieve effectiveness of online BCHC information.

This study evaluated presentation forms of effective online BCHC information. Other than the interactive characteristics of internet multimedia, it was also necessary to cover readability, so that people can maintain their memory and achieve learning. The

results of this study can be provided as a reference for designers in constructing design of online breast cancer prevention and health education information for effective transmission.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to express their thanks to the National Science Council, Taiwan, R.O.C., who have sponsored the research presented in this paper under Grant NSC 99-2410-H-224-020.

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